

Genetics of tolerance for iron toxicity in rice

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The lack of understanding about the genetics of tolerance for iron toxicity in rice has slowed the progress of breeding for tolerance for the disorder. We studied genetic effects through generation mean analysis and estimated heterosis and narrow-sense heritability using four rice varieties. CK4 and CK73 were tolerant of iron toxicity, ITA 330 and Bouaké 189 were susceptible. Two sets of populations were generated from crosses between tolerant and susceptible types. Cross I was between CK4 and ITA 330; CK73/Bouaké 189 constituted cross II.

For each cross, six generations (Table 1) were transplanted and tested separately in 5.5×2.5 -m iron-toxic blocks specially prepared to ensure uniformity. The experiment took place in Korhogo ($9^{\circ}22'N$, $5^{\circ}31'W$) in northern Côte d'Ivoire during the wet season (May-August 1996), using a randomized complete block design with three replications on an irrigated Ultisol lowland that contained 379 ppm Fe in soil solution at the beginning of the season.

Individual hills were scored for leaf symptom based on tolerance for iron toxicity at 75 d after transplanting. An earlier study had indicated that period to be the most appropriate in assessing *Oryza sativa* varieties for their reaction to iron toxicity.

In cross I, the F_1 hybrid had a mean score of 2.063, showing more tolerance than the tolerant parent (CK4), which scored 3.104 (1 = no symptoms; 9 = dead plants). Heterosis was estimated to be 1.042. In cross II, however, heterosis was absent. F_2 individuals showed a continuous distribution in both crosses (see figure).

In both crosses, the simple additive dominance model failed to fit the data. This suggested that the observed variation could be attributed to nonallelic interacting genes or epistatic genes, but not to additive and dominance genes alone. Estimations of these genetic effects based on Hayman's method are presented in Table 2. In both crosses, [d] and [h] were highly significant and negative. This implies that although nonallelic genes were present, most of the genes responsible for tolerance for iron toxicity were dominant.

The presence of epistatic genes may have led to the appearance of unexpected types in the progeny, which may represent real advances over their parents. In fact, transgressive segregation was observed in the F_2 of cross I, with some individuals falling outside the range of parents in both directions. This was probably due to effects of epistatic genes. In breeding for tolerance, breeders should therefore look for

the possibility of transgressive types occurring.

Narrow-sense heritabilities (h_n) were estimated to be 73.6% in cross I and 25.0% in cross II, indicating that the character can be inherited. The high h_n in cross I suggested that heritable genetic variability is possible even in early generation selection.

Distribution and mean of parents, F_1 and F_2 plants. The solid lines represent the range of the generations about their means (points).

Table 1. Generations of crosses used in the experiment.

Basic generations	Total number	
	CK4/ITA 330 (I)	CK73/Bouaké 189 (II)
Tolerant parent (P_1)	48	48
Susceptible parent (P_2)	48	48
F_1 ($P_1 \times P_2$)	24	24
F_2 (selfing of F_1)	120	144
B1 ($F_1 \times P_1$)	24	24
B2 ($F_1 \times P_2$)	24	24

Table 2. Estimation of additive, dominance, and interaction parameters with a six-parameter model of Hayman.

Parameter ^a	Cross I: CK4/ITA330			Cross II: CK73/Bouaké 189		
	Estimate	Std. error	Probability	Estimate	Std. error	Probability
m	4.6667	0.1180	<0.001	5.6181	0.0903	<0.001
[d]	-1.7083	0.2444	<0.001	-0.7500	0.2796	<0.001
[h]	-5.5521	0.6916	<0.001	-3.8160	0.7133	<0.001
[i]	-3.2500	0.6793	<0.001	-3.3056	0.66658	<0.001
[j]	-0.4479	0.2614	ns	0.1146	0.3069	ns
[l]	0.6875	1.1161	ns	3.8264	1.2821	0.01-0.001

^am = midparent value, [d] = balance of additive gene effects, [h] = balance of dominance gene effects, [i] = additive-additive gene interactions, [j] = additive-dominance gene interactions, [l] = dominance-dominance gene interactions. ns = not significant.